

Optimizing Federated Learning through Lightweight and Scalable Blockchain

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Abstract—In recent years, the increased focus on preserving data privacy, the advancements in machine learning, and the ongoing innovations in blockchain technology have sparked significant interest in implementing blockchain-based federated learning frameworks. Proposed solutions primarily focus on addressing the growing size of the blockchain in relation to machine learning algorithms, particularly the number of parameters involved in federated learning. However, the expanding blockchain scale results in increased time requirements, making many solutions impractical. In light of these issues, our research introduces a proof-of-concept for a lightweight, scalable, and modular blockchain network using Hyperledger Fabric to enhance federated learning. Performance evaluations using Hyperledger Caliper show that the proposed blockchain network effectively improves federated learning without compromising latency and throughput. Experimental results affirm blockchain’s proficiency in managing substantial transaction payloads from federated learning clients, especially with resource-intensive machine learning algorithms during training.

Index Terms—Blockchain, Federated Learning, Lightweight, Scalable, Privacy

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of intelligent and Internet of Things (IoT) devices, along with the influential impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) primarily demonstrated through Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) methodologies, has transformed data communication and storage. Notably, Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have showcased superior performance in diverse domains, including image classification [1], object detection [2], and natural language processing [3]. Concurrently, Large Language Models (LLMs) like ChatGPT [4], have extended the reach of generative models [5], [6] and Transformers [7], influencing various applications. This technological evolution holds significant importance in contemporary landscapes, particularly as AI tools become integral to smart devices, generating data with associated privacy concerns. In

addition, the data originating from local devices are inherently personal and sensitive, leading to strict access restrictions, particularly in the wake of stringent regulations like GDPR [8]. To tackle these challenges, sophisticated frameworks such as Federated Learning (FL) have emerged, reflecting the ongoing endeavor to safeguarding data privacy and integrity.

Federated learning, introduced in [9], revolutionizes ML with its decentralized paradigm. It enables model training across a network of edge devices or servers, preserving data localization unlike traditional centralized methods. By facilitating collaborative training on individual devices responsible for data generation, FL ensures robust data privacy preservation [10], confining sensitive information to local devices. Only model updates, in the form of aggregated gradients, are exchanged to enhance the global model iteratively.

The significant advancements in FL focus on diverse characteristics, as discussed in [11]. Methodologies prioritize model aggregation techniques [12], security protocols [13], or overall performance optimization [14], [15], contributing to a refined understanding, aiming to elevate the effectiveness of FL across various dimensions. To resolve the aforementioned challenges in data privacy and model security, ongoing efforts are focused on leveraging blockchain as the solution. Blockchain is anticipated to improve FL by utilizing its technology for the coordinator server, effectively mitigating the risk of a single point of failure in the FL process.

A blockchain is a decentralized digital ledger that securely stores and links data blocks using cryptographic techniques. Each block contains verifiable transactions, and their interconnection through cryptographic hashes ensures a secure and immutable [16] structure, enhancing data integrity [17] and resisting modification. Blockchain’s inherent transparency [18], [19] makes transactions accessible to all participants, fostering trust, particularly valuable in sectors like finance [20]. In essence, blockchain serves as a technical solution for decentralized and trustless database management.

In this research, we present a proof-of-concept (PoC) decen-

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tralized architecture based on blockchain, designed to deploy a resource-intensive FL framework for training a state-of-the-art object detector. The primary contributions of this work include:

- Introduction of a PoC infrastructure for a lightweight, scalable, and modular blockchain network, specifically designed to augment FL.
- Performance evaluations for the proposed PoC conducted using established benchmarking tools, demonstrating the effectiveness of the blockchain network in managing substantial transaction payloads generated by FL clients.

The structure of this paper unfolds as follows: This section serves as an Introduction, followed by the presentation of the Background in Section II. Section III delineates and thoroughly analyzes the concrete steps of our Methodology. Section IV engages in a comprehensive description of the experimental setup, followed by the presentation of the associated experimental results and the corresponding remarks in Section V. Finally, in Section VI we consolidate key findings and present concluding remarks, while also outline potential avenues for future research.

II. BACKGROUND & RELATED WORK

Federated Learning is an innovative decentralized ML training approach, evolving traditional centralized server reliance. While preserving data privacy at the local device level, it introduces new challenges critical for practical applications. To address these complexities, integrating blockchain technology into the FL framework is a promising solution. In the rest of this section, we discuss the primary challenges detailed in [21], [22], followed by Blockchain FL solutions designed for each challenge, concluding with a characterization and categorization of our proposed methodology.

a) Centralized processing: In the majority of FL frameworks, essential operations, including global model weight updates, are typically executed on a central server. While this centralized approach ensures the preservation of data privacy on local devices, it introduces vulnerabilities wherein a malicious actor could potentially infiltrate the central server. Such intrusion poses a threat to the integrity of the FL process, opening avenues for various attacks such as Man-in-the-Middle (MiTM) and data poisoning attacks. Recent studies, including [23], emphasize on the development of decentralized countermeasures through the integration of blockchain technology into the FL paradigm.

b) Lack of intensive mechanisms: Most FL applications, involving DNN training, face challenges due to high computational and resource demands, leading to security risks and client reluctance. Addressing these challenges necessitates the implementation of suitable incentives to motivate client engagement. Noteworthy contributions, such as [24], propose alternative reward structures, including data and mining rewards, while innovative reward calculation and distribution policies are suggested by [25].

The second facet of the incentivization challenge lies in ensuring fair reward distribution based on the quality and

quantity of contributed data. Research endeavors are directing attention towards Mobile Crowdsensing applications [26], whereas others, such as [27], focus on the specific nuances of FL, both aiming for an efficient reward mechanism that boosts participation while maintaining data quality.

c) Model security & data privacy: Concerning model security in FL, two primary threats are identified: data poisoning attacks [28] and Byzantine attacks [29]. Byzantine attacks involve intentional misinformation, disrupting collaborative model aggregation and jeopardizing global model confidentiality and availability. Solutions for Byzantine attacks in Blockchain FL, proposed in [30], leverage blockchain and homomorphic encryption, while [24] focuses on effective client selection.

Data poisoning attacks entail malicious devices injecting corrupted or manipulated data during training, compromising the model's performance and integrity. Addressing this concern, [31] suggests an intrusion detection method, and [32] proposes a fully decentralized approach utilizing blockchain technology. For maintaining data privacy with a central server, potential threats like model extraction attacks [33] and model inversion attacks [34] exist. Mitigating these risks, privacy-preserving mechanisms suggested in [35] aim to fortify security, safeguard against adversarial actions and ensure robustness of FL models.

d) Performance and Communication overhead: In this research category, the primary focus is on enhancing the Blockchain FL infrastructure's performance and communication. The objective is to enable FL to adapt to the increasing complexity of ML algorithms and the growing number of decentralized devices involved. Works like [36] aim to optimize blockchain node communication at the channel level. Additionally, [37] proposes an effective Blockchain FL infrastructure architecture with a detailed performance analysis, covering resource allocation, client selection, and data privacy. Moreover, solutions like those in [38] suggest sharding to optimize scalability concerning the growing number of connected devices in the FL process.

Our proposed methodology is designed to improve performance through the strategic utilization of blockchain technology employing a centralized processing approach. In addition, our method inherently addresses issues related to data privacy and model security, establishing a coupled approach as defined in [21]. Our primary objective centers on evaluating the efficacy of blockchain in integrating resource and energy intensive FL schemes that deploy state-of-the-art object detectors, characterized by millions of parameters.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section we will describe our approach and outline the architecture of our proposed framework. The primary focus of our study is to assess the capacity of a blockchain network to manage substantial transaction payloads generated by FL clients. These clients are actively engaged in training large-scale deep learning models that encompass million of parameters. Figure 1 depicts our solution which is separated

Fig. 1: Blockchain-based Federated Learning proposed framework architecture

into three components, the FL process, the client application responsible for orchestrating transaction submission in the blockchain, and the blockchain network.

Federated learning operates autonomously from the blockchain network. In greater detail, the central server broadcast the global model to the nodes (FL clients) and the first round of training is initiated. Upon completion of the local model training by the FL clients using their data, the central server aggregates these local models and consolidates them into a global model. Simultaneously, each FL client utilizes its application to transmit local model updates (neural network parameters) to the blockchain network. This data is structured into a transaction proposal, which utilizes a smart contract to generate read-write set. Once the transaction proposal is formulated, peers verify the included signatures. Following verification, the transaction undergoes validation and commitment, ultimately being incorporated into a block within the blockchain.

Ultimately, in our implementation, we store the neural network parameters into the blockchain to enhance traceability, being able to restore the model to a previous state, and safeguard the global model from potentially malicious users who may poison the model.

A. Federated Learning

We have integrated the FL service in our experiments using the Flower Framework¹ to train a deep learning model tailored explicitly for object detection tasks, employing the YOLOv8² algorithm. Federated learning allows us to harness the power of decentralized training across multiple clients while respecting data privacy constraints.

The central server assumes the pivotal role of aggregating and computing the global model, while the distributed clients,

each possessing local data, are tasked with training their respective local models and providing updates to the global model.

As we delve into the following section, we will elucidate the incorporation of Hyperledger Fabric³ into this ecosystem, outlining how this blockchain framework enhances the federated learning process.

B. Blockchain

Hyperledger Fabric offers a permissioned blockchain environment, ensuring that participation in the network is restricted to authorized entities. This permissioned model aligns with the privacy and security considerations inherent in our FL scenario. Moreover, the scalability and modularity provided by Hyperledger Fabric align precisely with the specific requirements of our application.

The Hyperledger Fabric network is composed of peers. These peers play a crucial role in maintaining a distributed ledger, validating transactions, and executing smart contracts. The deployment of peers in Docker⁴ containers ensures a direct and flawless integration between the blockchain network and the ML environment.

An essential component of Hyperledger Fabric is the ordering service, which manages the orderly inclusion of transactions into blocks. This service guarantees a consistent transaction order across all peers, contributing to the overall integrity of the ledger. Additionally, the presence of smart contracts, or chaincode, allows us to encode and enforce the rules governing transactions, ensuring a secure and transparent storage of local models updated in the ledger.

Another feature contributing to our implementation's robustness is its consensus mechanism. In our setup, we leverage the Raft consensus algorithm [39]. Raft is well-suited for scenarios requiring a straightforward and lightweight consensus

¹<https://flower.dev>

²<https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>

³<https://github.com/hyperledger/fabric>

⁴<https://www.docker.com/>

protocol. It operates by electing a leader among the nodes, which then coordinates the consensus process. This consensus mechanism ensures that all peers within the network agree on the order and validity of transactions, fostering trust and reliability.

In the proposed solution, all peers are part of the same channel within the Hyperledger Fabric network. This deliberate design choice aims to streamline the interactions and transactions within a single channel, simplifying the network structure and reducing the overall complexity. This channel-centric approach fosters a cohesive environment for FL operations, facilitating a seamless flow of information and updates between the peers.

C. Client Application

We employed the Hyperledger Fabric Gateway SDK⁵ in our client application, a fundamental element within the Hyperledger Fabric blockchain network. This gateway orchestrates the necessary actions for transaction submission and ledger state queries on behalf of client applications. Consequently, our client application only requires a connection to a single endpoint within the blockchain network.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

In order to validate the efficacy of our methodology, we conducted a series of experiments, aimed at assessing its performance and functionality in terms of scalability, modularity, and the amount of the required computational resources.

Firstly, we implemented controlled scenarios to evaluate the interaction between FL clients and the blockchain network. These scenarios simulated various transaction payloads, allowing us to gauge the system’s ability to handle different magnitudes of data generated during the training of large-scale deep learning models.

Subsequently, we examined the responsiveness and efficiency of the blockchain network in processing these substantial transaction payloads. The experiments included stress tests, enabling us to identify potential bottlenecks and optimize performance under high-demand conditions.

Table I offers a summary of the experimental configuration employed to validate the effectiveness of our proposed solution.

A. Federated Learning Setup

In the framework of FL, the central server is mandatory in orchestrating the FL clients, while they compute the local models. Local model updates, generated independently by five FL clients, are aggregated at the central server through the application of the FedAvg aggregation strategy, implemented iteratively over ten rounds. This iterative approach supports the convergence and overall performance of the FL process, fostering a more robust and accurate global model.

The selected model for training within the framework of our proposed methodology is YOLOv8, a state-of-the-art DNN designed for object detection applications. YOLOv8 demonstrates superior performance in this task by delivering

accurate results in real-time. Notably, it comprises 3.2 million parameters, highlighting the considerable size of the neural network and the computational intensity associated with its training procedure.

B. Blockchain Setup

In our setup, each component is deployed within its own Docker container. Illustrated in Figure 2, our blockchain network architecture features two separate entities. One is dedicated to the orderer (orderer organization), while the other accommodates the five peers (peer organization) that collectively form the network. Furthermore, certificate authorities are integrated into the network, each one associated with the distinct organizations. The network utilizes a single channel that includes all peers and the orderer. The smart contract is deployed across all peers, enabling them to engage with the ledger (read and update the ledger). Furthermore, each peer in the network possesses a copy of the ledger.

Fig. 2: Blockchain network architecture

C. Dataset

In the context of our research exploration, the construction safety computer vision dataset [40] that is part of the Roboflow Benchmark [41] served as a fundamental component. This dataset, comprising 1206 images and encompassing more than 7000 annotations, was curated to address diverse scenarios related to construction site safety. The dataset is organized into five distinct classes, each vital for safety assessment: person, helmet, no-helmet, vest, and no-vest.

D. Evaluation

We assess the performance of our implementation using Hyperledger Caliper⁶, an open-source benchmarking tool designed for testing smart contracts deployed on Hyperledger Fabric. This tool simplifies the stress testing of our blockchain network by autonomously assessing functions within the smart contract through the generation of transactions. Additionally, we set a time limit of 60 seconds for every configuration

⁵<https://github.com/hyperledger/fabric-gateway>

⁶<https://github.com/hyperledger/caliper>

TABLE I: Experimental Configuration Setup

Component	Version	CPU	GPU	RAM	NVMe SSD
Hyperledger Fabric	2.5.4	M1 Pro 8-core CPU	M1 Pro 14-core GPU	32GB	500GB
Hyperledger Caliper	0.5.0				
Hyperledger Fabric Gateway	1.4.0				
Flower Framework	1.5.0				

instance that was executed in the experiments, as depicted in Table II. It is essential to highlight that, to the best of our knowledge, the current work represents the first initiative in subjecting Hyperledger Caliper to stress tests on the ARM CPU architecture. The subsequent monitoring of responses allows us to derive metrics such as latency, transaction throughput, and success rates.

1) *Latency*: Latency refers to the delay or time lag introduced during the communication and synchronization processes within the blockchain network. It is measured as the total time required for a transaction to be completed. Specifically, we target on the Average and Minimum Latency.

2) *Throughput (Transactions per second - TPS)*: Throughput signifies the speed at which transactions are processed and confirmed within the network. It quantifies the efficiency of the system by measuring the volume of reliably processed transactions per second, influencing the overall scalability and responsiveness of the blockchain. It is formally defined as:

$$TPS = \frac{N}{\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

, where N is the number of successfully completed transactions and Δt the selected time interval (measured in seconds).

3) *Transaction Success Rate (TSR)*: Transaction Success Rate denotes the percentage of transactions successfully executed and confirmed. It gauges the reliability and accuracy of transaction processing, reflecting the system's dependability and is described as:

$$TSR = \left(\frac{N}{T}\right) \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

, where N is the number of successfully completed transactions and T the total number of attempted transactions.

In our experimental setup, we conduct tests with varying configuration settings including MaxMessageCount, AbsoluteMaxBytes, and PreferredMaxBytes. These settings are integral to the configuration setup of Hyperledger Fabric, as they can significantly influence the efficiency and the performance of our architecture, under different conditions. MaxMessageCount denotes the maximum number of transactions a block can hold while AbsoluteMaxBytes and PreferredMaxBytes represent the maximum and preferred block size in megabytes, respectively.

Eventually, a critical task within our blockchain network involves updating ledger assets at the conclusion of each round in the FL process. To simulate this, we generate numerous local model updates, creating transaction proposals on the

blockchain. Finally, Transaction Load setting refers to the maximum number of pending transactions in a System Under Test (SUT).

V. RESULTS

In our exploration of the benchmarks, we extended our analysis by incorporating diverse workloads to comprehensively evaluate the robustness of our solution. Initially, we configured our Hyperledger Caliper with the assumption of five FL clients, and subsequently, we adjusted the number of workers accordingly to match this setup.

For the experimental scenario, we deliberately selected the YOLOv8 algorithm, renowned for its computationally demanding nature. YOLOv8 necessitates bigger time commitments, often spanning minutes or even hours. Taking into consideration the time required for training a YOLOv8 algorithm and the assumption that FL clients may not complete training simultaneously, our experimental design did not encompass exhaustive trials. Instead, we made strategic choices in configuring the settings of the Hyperledger Fabric blockchain network.

Table II provides a comprehensive display of the experimental outcomes is accompanied by detailed information on all configuration settings. It is noteworthy to highlight that the Transaction Success Rate (TSR) remains consistently at 100%, underscoring the robustness of our solution in diverse conditions.

1) *Configuration-1*: We adjusted the default settings in the Hyperledger Fabric configuration file to better suit our requirements. By configuring the MaxMessageCount to 10, we determined the optimal size for blocks, ensuring they accommodate a sufficient number of transactions. Setting this as our baseline allowed us to explore the correlation between these values in block creation without waiting for an excessive number of transactions.

Consequently, the overall throughput suffered under low transaction loads. This was attributed to the blocks not being fully filled with transactions, resulting in block timeouts, a mechanism to handle conditions where a block has not been added to the chain within the specified time of two seconds. As a consequence, the orderer was not fully utilized, due to the block timeout principle. The average latency of the high transaction load is degraded cause of the overall size of the block. Building on this baseline, we experimented with different configurations to delve deeper into system behavior.

2) *Configuration-2*: We define an AbsoluteMaxBytes parameter sufficiently large to accommodate significant models but still adhering to the maximum recommended size of 49

TABLE II: Experimental results for the five configurations under test with respect to the increasing transaction loads.

Configuration	MaxMessageCount	AbsoluteMaxBytes (MB)	PreferredMaxBytes (MB)	Transaction Load	TPS	Average Latency (s)	Min Latency (s)	TSR (%)
1	10	20	10	5	5.8	1.54	0.65	100
				10	6.4	1.96	0.81	100
				20	6.9	2.66	0.80	100
2	20	40	20	5	3.2	2.54	0.67	100
				10	5.1	2.25	0.59	100
				20	6.7	2.58	0.55	100
3	1	40	20	5	8.7	0.95	0.27	100
				10	9.3	1.30	0.37	100
				20	9.8	2.04	0.24	100
4	20	10	2	5	8.3	1.00	0.41	100
				10	9.3	1.33	0.64	100
				20	9.3	1.99	0.29	100
5	30	40	30	5	3.7	2.23	0.85	100
				10	4.7	2.74	1.10	100
				20	5.4	3.14	0.67	100

MB, as specified in the Hyperledger Fabric documentation. This recommendation considers the headroom required for the default gRPC ⁷ size limit of 100 MB and accounts for potential message expansion during communication. As previously stated, the throughput of the system experiences a decline under high transaction loads due to the overall size of the blocks. This issue also impacts the average latency; although we can accommodate up to 20 transactions in a block, the validation of transactions is not sufficiently fast. Therefore, there are instances where the block times out before reaching full capacity.

3) *Configuration-3*: Given the intricate setting of our FL process, we formulated the hypothesis that each block in the blockchain would encapsulate a solitary transaction. Our objective is to examine the network under low utilization (low send rates of data) without compromising the latency.

Upon analyzing different transaction loads, we observe that the performance remains relatively stable across various workloads. However, it is evident that the overall latency for transaction completion (block creation) increases as the number of pending transactions rises, reaching saturation for a single orderer.

4) *Configuration-4*: In this setup, PreferredMaxBytes was intentionally set to 2MB, aiming to mimic a network capable of handling large message volumes. However, due to large model testing, the block contained a maximum of 2 transactions, yielding results similar to our previous configuration.

5) *Configuration-5*: Increasing the block size further exposed latency issues during high-throughput transactions, similar to Configuration-2. The block timeout principle influenced overall transaction latency, highlighting the impact of the chosen parameters on system performance.

Scalability plays a crucial role in meeting the growing requirements of federated learning procedures. The findings indicate that the rise in transactions per second (TPS) does

not correlate with an increase in Average Latency. Additionally, the Minimum Latency metrics underscore the system's capacity to manage heightened workloads while maintaining minimal impact on performance. As indicated by Table II, the most effective arrangement is the third configuration. It attains a TPS of 9.8 with minimal latency, just 0.24 seconds. These findings highlight the capacity of the blockchain network in verifying a large volume of transactions, including data from the federated learning process.

Figure 3 presents the CPU utilization for the Docker container instances regarding the settings of *Configuration 3*. The primary CPU consumption is attributed to peer nodes, which perform the verification of federated learning results, leading to increased CPU demand. Hyperledger Caliper was utilized for performance monitoring, ensuring that the experiments did not exceed the hardware's CPU capabilities, with an experimental setup equipped with 8 cores (equivalent to 800% total CPU capacity). The evaluation indicates diverse resource consumption across components based on their functions within the "execute-order-validate" architecture of Fabric. Moreover, the increase and subsequent decrease in CPU utilization are indicative of the workload pattern in the container instance. The initial increase is due to the ramp-up phase where the system is processing an accumulating number of transactions, leading to a peak where the system is at its maximum capacity. Finally, after the peak at 60 seconds, the workload decreases as the system begins to complete and clear transactions, which reduces the demand on the CPU, hence the observed reduction in utilization.

This fact suggests that our system operates efficiently, unlikely to reach full CPU utilization, emphasizing its lightweight design. Our approach to analyzing CPU utilization is inspired by the methodologies presented in [42], which have significantly influenced our monitoring techniques and experimental setup.

Modularity constitutes a key feature within our proposed solution, rendering it a dynamic and versatile platform suitable

⁷<https://grpc.io/>

Fig. 3: CPU Utilization per container deployed during the stress test. Seven containers deployed in total: one for each of the five peers, one for the orderer, and one for the peers chaincode

for a diverse range of applications. The proposed framework demonstrates the capability to incorporate a diverse range of deep learning algorithms, offering users the flexibility to select and deploy FL models customized to their specific needs. This modular nature of this framework expedites the implementation of future upgrades and expansions.

Ultimately, these experiments yielded valuable insights into the performance and scalability of the solution across diverse conditions, contributing to the ongoing refinement of our modular and efficient approach for real-world scenarios.

VI. CONCLUSION

In summary, our comprehensive framework seamlessly integrates FL with the robust capabilities of Hyperledger Fabric, aiming to tackle the challenges associated with handling substantial transaction payloads generated in FL processes. The selection of Hyperledger Fabric as our blockchain framework is rooted in its permissioned blockchain environment, modular architecture, and scalability, which align effectively with the privacy and security considerations inherent in our FL scenario. The selected lightweight consensus mechanism promotes increased transaction throughput without introducing latency. Our experimental results affirm that the blockchain network can extend FL capabilities without compromising efficiency.

As part of our ongoing and future efforts, we strive to enhance our implementation by incorporating the FL process directly within the blockchain network. This improvement would empower each peer in the blockchain to locally aggregate the global model, eliminating the necessity for a central server. Moreover, we plan to upgrade our framework to support x86 CPU architecture for better compatibility and performance. Finally, we explore the potential of incorporating other consensus mechanisms to increase the resilience of our blockchain network against malicious activities.

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